

Elongation ability in deepwater rices

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We studied the elongation ability of 12 deepwater rice varieties and 24 advanced breeding lines during 1989 wet season. Entries seeded in pots were submerged in 120-cm-deep water 42-49 d after seeding.

Internode, leaf sheath, and leaf blade lengths were measured on 10 plants before and after flooding. Recovery or submergence tolerance was scored 10 d after water was drained.

By and large, the traditional floating rices had higher total elongation than did the breeding lines (see table). Total plant elongation after 7 d water treatment ranged from 8.5 cm (entry ACC33745 was rejected and is not in the table) to 66.5 cm (TCA4).

TCA4 had the highest internode

Plant elongation and regeneration ability of rices with different deepwater survival strategies.^a

Variety	Elongation (cm)			Submergence tolerance score
	Internode	Leaf sheath	Leaf blade	
TCA4	<u>51.5</u>	7.6	7.4	7
NDGR401	<u>49.0</u>	2.7	3.7	5
NDGR406	<u>42.7</u>	8.0	5.0	5
NDGR404	<u>42.3</u>	3.7	<u>16.4</u>	5
ACC38876	<u>34.3</u>	9.4	7.3	5
Jalmagna	<u>31.3</u>	5.0	6.0	9
NDGR402	<u>28.4</u>	6.3	<u>18.6</u>	3
920356	22.0	4.7	<u>20.3</u>	3
IR11141-6-1-4	16.9	8.4	<u>18.7</u>	5
Nam Sagui 19	13.1	9.6	2.7	3
IR39657-4-502-1-3-2	12.0	4.7	12.0	5
TCA7819	11.0	<u>20.3</u>	10.0	5
IR39657-B-B-1	4.0	<u>15.7</u>	4.0	5
ACC18973	2.0	<u>16.0</u>	5.0	3
FR 13A	0.4	<u>20.6</u>	4.0	3

^aUnderlining indicates relatively high reliance of the plant on the corresponding survival strategy.

elongation, followed by NDGR404 and NDGR406.

Leaf sheath and leaf blade elongation as high as 15.7-20.6 cm were recorded in 920356, ACC18973, TCA7819, NDGR402, IR39657-B-B-1, and FR13A. Since leaf elongation ability is limited, these entries might be suitable for areas that have sudden floods of limited depth.

Varieties with submergence tolerance scores 1-3 will be helpful in areas prone to

sudden submergence.

Higher elongation values indicate relatively high reliance on the corresponding survival strategy. Some varieties rely on internode elongation, leaf (sheath, blade) elongation, and/or submergence tolerance. Breeding strategies could incorporate some or all of these survival characters, depending on the target area. □

Pest resistance—diseases

Utilization of sources of resistance to bacterial blight (BE) in China

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We screened 99 rice cultivars and lines against BB caused by *Xanthomonas oryzae* pv. *oryzae* (Xoo) at CNRRI Experiment Station during Apr-Oct 1990.

Thirty-day-old seedlings were transplanted in two rows of 14 hills each at 20- × 20-cm spacing, with two replications. One row each of local susceptible check Jin-Gang 30 and resistant check IR26 were transplanted between each entry and around the experimental field.

The plot was fertilized with 75-37.5-25 kg NPK/ha.

Seven pathogenic groups of Xoo with varying virulence, based on their reaction on five Chinese differentials, were provided by Yin Shangzhi, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences (Table 1).

Test plants were clip-inoculated with a concentration of 3×10^8 CFU/ml from maximum tillering to initial booting stage.

Disease incidence was scored 21 d after inoculation.

Eight varieties showed resistance to the pathogenic groups (Table 2). They have good agronomic traits and high yield potential, and have been used as resistance sources for breeding.

Given the geographical distribution of the BB pathogenic groups and the rice varietal types appropriate for different rice cropping regions, *Xa-3* resistance sources are best in japonica rice cropping

Table 1. Pathogenic groups of Xoo in China.

Pathogenic group	Representative isolate	Reaction ^a on indicated differential varieties				
		Jin-Gang 30	Tetep	Nan-Jing 15	Java 14	IR26
I	JS97-2	S	R	R	R	R
II	KS-1-21	S	S	R	R	R
III	JS158-2	S	S	S	R	R
IV	Zhejiang 173	S	S	S	S	R
V	1358	S	S	R	R	S
VI	OS-198	S	R	S	R	R
VII	JS49-6	S	R	S	S	R

^aR = resistant, S = susceptible.